
Tarannum Interactive Audiobook Model: Towards a Harmonious Assimilation of Information and Communication Technology into Quranic Education

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Abstract

This article presents an investigation on the effectiveness of audiobook application in *Tarannum* learning for beginners, especially among Muslims with no foundation in *Tarannum*. This study aims to analyze the suitability of this alternative *Tarannum* learning method for beginners, as well as to identify the appropriate content to be incorporated in the audiobook. Finally, this study also aims to develop a model of the new platform for *Tarannum* learning; the *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook Model. The qualitative approach is used in this study to collect the library data from books, articles, and journals to form a research model. Furthermore, this study also uses the interview method by asking relevant questions to some experienced respondents to get their views on the suitability, requirements and potential issues on the application of audiobooks for *Tarannum* learning. This study found that there are existing studies on the use of audiobooks for the teaching and learning process but not in the context of *Tarannum*. Therefore, this study has contributed in developing an audiobook model. This model will be used as the main reference to guide the development of the actual *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook, which can further facilitate beginners and students in learning *Tarannum* al-Quran more effectively.

Keywords: Al-Quran; *Tarannum*; Audiobook; Quranic Education; Educational Technology; *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook

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Introduction

Reciting the Qur'an is one of the preferred acts of worship by Muslims to the Almighty God, Allah S.W.T. This Qur'an recitation will be even more graceful and appealing if complemented with the *Tarannum* recitation. In the field of Quranic education, *Tarannum* is an art of recitation in which rhythm is varied according to certain intonations and voice projections with the purpose of harmonizing the sound (Jamali & Tengku Kasim, 2020). In adapting *Tarannum* while reciting the Qur'an, one has to do it according to the correct principles of *tajwid*, or Arabic elocution and in a melodious voice, while conveying the meaning of the Qur'an effectively (Hasbullah et al., 2020). Reciting Qur'an with *Tarannum* and correct *tajwid* rules are necessary so that the meaning of the Quranic verses will be preserved. The majority of Islamic scholars agreed that reciting the Qur'an with *Tarannum* is a *Sunnah* since the Prophet Muhammad S.A.W has encouraged Muslims to recite the Qur'an properly and in a melodious voice. There are several hadiths on this matter and one of them is:

ليس منا من لم يتغن بالقرآن

Meaning: "It is not from our (ummah) group, anyone who does not Tarannum with the Quran."

Among the objectives of *Tarannum* is to achieve perfection in the recitation or *tartil* as recommended by the Qur'an and Hadith. This shows that *Tarannum* is an important knowledge and needs to be learned by all Muslims to get a perfect recitation of the Qur'an. However, there are still many Muslims who are unable to recite Qur'anic *Tarannum* competently, and thus, this knowledge should be exposed from an early age. Moreover, some Muslim students who have learned Qur'anic *Tarannum* are also unable to read the Qur'an with good *tajwid* and *Tarannum*. One of the causes of this failure is the lack of learning aids to better understand *Tarannum*. Also, some educators do not have the appropriate or up-to-date materials in teaching *Tarannum*. In fact, teaching aids are very important to ensure that the teaching process can be executed smoothly and effectively. This is mainly because the content of teaching presented could be followed better by students with the help of teaching aids. Surprisingly, thus far, although research on *Tarannum* is common, but no one made it in the context of audiobooks. On the other hand, there are also research on audiobooks that are widely used in learning, but it is not available for *Tarannum*. Thus, this study intends to develop an audiobook model as a preliminary overview to the actual audiobook to be developed later which will facilitate Muslims in learning Qur'anic *Tarannum* more effectively.

Problem Statement

Nowadays, there are different approaches and tools for teaching and learning, including audiobooks. The method of learning using audiobooks is widely used in 21st-century education. Indeed, it has been accepted as one of the useful and effective methods in education. The applicability of this method has become salient during the recent pandemic, whereby the physical interactions between educators and students become taboo. However, despite its limitless negative impacts, the Covid-19 pandemic has also provided a great opportunity for the audiobook application in teaching and learning. Audiobooks have been widely used in learning the knowledge of the Qur'an, especially in *tajwid* and *qiraat* but unfortunately, not in the field of *Tarannum*. This is a great prospect, and an effort needs to be done. Therefore, this study proposes the *Tarannum* audiobook model that can be implemented among Muslims. It will be a great learning aid as it is convenient not only for beginners but also for those who are interested to learn *Tarannum*. This audiobook model is an alternative on how the knowledge could be spread to those who want to learn *Tarannum* in an interactive and engaging approach. The main objective of this study is to develop a model of the audiobook for *Tarannum* learning. In order to achieve this main objective, some sub-objectives are formulated: (i) To identify Qur'anic learning methods for the audiobook, (ii) To identify the suitable content to be included in the *Tarannum* audiobook model, and (iii) To develop a *Tarannum* audiobook model.

Literature Review

The prior studies on the effectiveness of audiobooks in education can be found in abundance. For example, there is a study that found that the audio development for the *Pendidikan Islam* textbook is very helpful especially for visually impaired students (Nurulthoilah et al., 2018). Similarly, Omar (2017) has conducted a study focusing on the children's digital books published by local publishers in Malaysia. It was discovered

that the variety of publications in the book industry indirectly reflects the civilization of a society. He concluded that publishers, agencies, individuals, and partners involved in this matter should take the opportunity to use the available technology platforms to improve the quality of creative educational content. Furthermore, the audio-visual media or better known as hearing aids are found to be very effective in teaching and learning in most subjects, including Islamic Education. This media has the ability to attract learners' attention in Islamic education (Kaimin & Mohd Aderi Che Noh, 2016). The audiobooks are also very practical, for instance, by relying only on one sense (listening), learning can be done while doing other activities (Anwas et al., 2014). Moreover, it was found that most educators had a positive perception of multimedia teaching aids. Nevertheless, there is no doubt that some technical barriers exist in the implementation of technological teaching aids (Ab Halim & Siti Fatimah, 2010). Therefore, educators need to be flexible when choosing the right resources to create digital content. In light of this, one of the suitable methods is audiobook (Rashed et al., 2008).

There are many more successful examples of the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) integration into education that can be extracted from the literature. For instance, Hussin et al. (2018) investigate the feasibility of the implementation of a mobile application created by combining the elements of *naqli* and *aqli* as an attempt to introduce the *Riwayat Warsh* recitation to Muslim society. As a result, a *qiraat* teaching and learning smartphone app on *Riwayat Warsh* called Ez-Warsh has been successfully created in the Malay language. Similarly, an e-Tajweed application was found as helpful to students to learn the Holy Qur'an rules. The students were all attracted to the application for its colorful interfaces and the various learning activity provided in the application (Said, 2012). Similar positive trends can be seen in several other studies (Hajarul et al., 2010; Latif et al., 2020). Therefore, it is interesting to investigate whether the use of an audiobook could produce a similar result or vice-versa.

Research Methodology

This study uses a design and development type of research. It is a multimethod research design that entails the application of multiple sources of data or research methods to the investigation of one or more but highly linked research questions. This type of research design is chosen since this study is about the development of an audiobook model, which involves multiple but related types of data. The ADDIE model is used in this study. This ADDIE model is very effective in providing materials to audiobook developers. It will make the development of audiobooks easier. *Tarannum* audiobook model is developed according to these phases: Analysis, Design, Development, Implement, and Evaluation.

Analysis Phase

This is the first phase in the ADDIE model for design and development research where information on the context and environment is collected. In this phase, this study listed out objectives of the *Tarannum* audiobook model by analyzing the *Tarannum* learning method according to a school syllabus. Next, the suitable content of a *Tarannum* audiobook model was identified. Through the analysis, the audiobook requirements based on learners' perspectives were also identified at the end of this stage.

Design Phase

In this second phase, the findings of the analysis were used to guide the design. The objective of this phase is to design an audiobook model for *Tarannum* learning. This phase is more focused on examining both the design and the material needed to support the audiobook model. In addition, more attention was given to the content of *Tarannum* to be included in the audiobook model.

Development Phase

The objective of this phase is to develop an audiobook model for the beginner to learn *Tarannum*. Once the learning has been designed, the development phase will focus on creating and developing the materials of the audiobook. The study created and assembled content from the design phase to build the audiobook model.

Implementation Phase

The implementation reflects the level of modification needed for this audiobook model, so that maximum efficiency and positive results could be obtained. This is the stage where this study strives to redesign, update, and edit internal content to ensure that the *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook model can be delivered effectively.

Evaluation Phase

The last phase of the ADDIE model is evaluation. In this phase, the evaluation of the audiobook model by the supervisor and *Tarannum* expert was conducted. Assessments were done to specifically check on designs such as the content and multimedia elements in the audiobook model that has been produced.

Data Collection

Document Analysis

The main method used in this study is document analysis. The related documents such as notes, transcripts, books, newspapers and magazines were analyzed during the analysis and design phase to gather the desired data. In addition, the need for an audiobook for beginners to learn *Tarannum* was listed out from the literature review. During the design phase, the study analyzed the document to decide the lesson plan and specified the suitable contents to be included in the audiobook model.

Interview

In the evaluation phase, the study conducted an interview regarding audiobooks for beginners. The interview is carried out to ensure understanding of the design, relevant content and outcome of the *Tarannum* audiobook model.

Sample and Respondents

The sample usually represents the population to generalize the findings (Education Center, n.d.). Meanwhile, sampling is the selection of a subset of individuals from a statistical population to estimate the overall characteristics of the population. There are a variety of samples or participants involved in this study. In the design phase, the samples used were some parts of the Qur'an verses based on the basic seven *maqamat* in *Tarannum* learning. In addition, six participants were involved in the interview session.

Analysis and Findings

For the interview, a total of six respondents were invited. These respondents have vast *Tarannum* knowledge as explained in Table 1. The findings of this interview are elaborated in the following sections.

Table 1

Respondents for the Interview

Research Participants (RP)	Gender	Job
PK 1	Male	Teacher
PK2	Male	Lecturer
PK3	Male	Teacher
PK4	Female	Teacher
PK5	Female	Teacher
PK6	Female	Student

The Use of Audiobooks as Teaching Aids

The findings of this semi-structured interview have encouraged this study to develop the proposed *Tarannum* audiobook model. It is found that RP 1, RP 4, and RP 5 have positively responded to the need to use audiobooks as teaching aids, stated:

“... great technology for beginners to know *Tarannum* and very helpful. Suitable for beginners...” (RP 1)

“...very helpful...” (RP 4)

“... very helpful for teachers who are less skilled in *Tarannum* and also for students to do *Tarannum* revision at home ...” (RP 5)

The Comprehension Through the Audiobook

Some participants also stated that beginners will find it easier to understand the information presented through audio. This is proved by the following statements:

“... great technology for beginners to know *Tarannum* and there should include recitation examples from good reciters...” (RP 1)

“... very helpful for someone new to *Tarannum*...” (RP 5)

The Effectiveness of Audiobooks in Tarannum Knowledge

In addition, RP 1, RP 3, RP 4, RP 5, and RP 6 looked at the effectiveness of audiobook models in *Tarannum* knowledge. These are some of their responses.

“... gives some kind of positive effect to the beginner, and teachers don't have to repeat the same recitation ...” (RP 1)

“...Its effectiveness is quite good for someone who studies the science of *Tarannum* ...” (RP 5)

Audiobook Content

The interview also discovered that RP 1, RP 2, RP 3, RP 4, RP 5, and RP 6 have optimistically responded to the content that can be included in the audiobook in terms of verses and content selections related to *Tarannum*. These are some of their remarks.

“...short and easy-to-recite verses ...” (RP 1)

“...The verses included should correspond to the beginner level. Not suitable if too high because the target is only for beginners. Then include the main essence of the 7 songs of *Tarannum* ...” (RP 2)

“.... surahs and songs should be fun and suitable for beginners who want to learn *Tarannum* ...” (RP 3)

Audiobook Model

This study is designed in accordance with the *Tarannum* learning format. In terms of syllabus, the *Tarannum* audiobook model is similar to the conventional *Tarannum* learning method using books. However, what differentiates this model is that it is designed using learning methods that are easy for users to understand. In addition, users could learn *Tarannum* by listening to the audio loaded in it. This model was developed as an initial design to the actual *Tarannum* audiobook which will be developed later. There are several resources utilized, which were taken from books and articles related to *Tarannum*.

There are seven sections in this audiobook model that explains the seven types of *Tarannum* namely *Bayyati*, *Nahwand*, *Rast*, *Sikah*, *Jiharkah*, *Soba* and *Hijjaz*. Each of the types is incorporated with audio practices, which enables users to learn *Tarannum* by using listening methods. The users can pause and playback the audio where it allows them to follow the recitation styles according to a certain type of *Tarannum*. They can learn the technique of how to recite the *Surah* by listening to it. There are seven chosen *Surah* assigned for each *Tarannum* method, which are al-Fatihah, al-Masad, al-Kafirun, Quraysh, al-Ikhlash, al-Fil and an-Nasr.

This audiobook is designed using the easy-to-learn *Tarannum* method which is suitable for beginners who have no basic in *Tarannum*.

Audiobook Flow Design

To develop this audiobook model, this study used a linear flow chart as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Flowchart of *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook Model

After collecting the data, this study began to design and develop the low fidelity prototype of the audiobook. The storyboard is used to convey the concept and style of the audiobook model. Next, during the development phase, the actual production of model requirements was performed. This involves several processes such as text creation, background layout design, interface design, and button activation. It also requires media acquisition as specified in the audiobook model design. During the development phase, all audio, video, and text are collected, prepared or created (Cooley, 2000). Later, the multimedia elements such as graphics, text, and audio were designed and created in the pre-authoring process. Figure 2 shows one of the designed pages in the *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook Model.

Figure 2. An Example of Page in the Tarannum Interactive Audiobook

Discussion and Conclusion

To develop a model of an interactive *Tarannum* audiobook, a lot of effort is required, especially to understand the Qur'an and *Tarannum* learning methods. Modern learning methods nowadays have used more advanced methods than ever before. With today's technology, it is possible to create more effective and interactive learning methods that will benefit all users. In applying technology in education, the combination of audio, video, animation and other multimedia elements could attract the learners' attention and at the same time help them to easily understand the contents (Rahman et al., 2011). Today's modern technologies can also be expanded in the context of the Qur'an and Islamic education. Hence, Muslims need to take advantage of the various facilities and technologies available to enhance the Qur'an and Islamic knowledge. Several teaching aids have been applied in the Qur'an and Islamic teaching and learning, for example using CD-ROMs, websites, mobile applications, audiobooks, and so on. However, the selection of technological teaching aids needs to be done carefully, especially in Qur'an and Islamic Education so that it is appropriate and can be integrated with traditional teaching methods (Tamuri et al., 2012).

Tarannum learning technique can be improvised, but without leaving the *talaqi* and *musyafahah* methods because they are *Sunnah* of the Prophet and his companions. Other methods such as ICT, CD, audio, video, graphics, and many more can be considered as it most probably would increase interest, attracts attention, easy to use, is not tied to individuals, timely and interactive. This study has successfully created a new *Tarannum* learning method in form of an audiobook. The use of audiovisual in teaching has a very good effect. Audio elements are said to create an interesting atmosphere and will result in more focus on what people want to convey (Ahmad Rizal M. & Yahya B., 2008). When it comes to content that can be incorporated into audiobooks for beginners, it must consist of basic content that is suitable for *Tarannum* learning. This can celebrate the whole ages to venture into the field of *Tarannum*. Looking at the content of previous works, they were divided or limited to certain groups. As for this study, the content is analyzed and identified to make sure it suits all ages regardless of children or adults.

The most important content is the introduction to *Tarannum* which includes its meaning as well as the history of *Tarannum* itself. From here, beginners are more likely to understand what *Tarannum* all is about before jumping into the type of *Tarannum*. Next, the content that can be included is the main core of seven *Tarannum* songs. Having stated the meaning of *Tarannum* and its history, the types of *Tarannum* can also be explained. *Tarannum* has seven types, or known as *maqam*, namely, *Bayyati*, *Nahwand*, *Rast*, *Sikah*, *Jiharkah*, *Soba* and *Hijjaz*. It is crucial to include these in the audiobook because it is the first measure of *Tarannum* learning. From here, beginners will begin to learn the characteristics and role of each *maqam*. Next, the selection of

verses to be included in this audiobook model is also vital and should consider learners' points of view. In this study, most of the respondents suggested using simple and short verses. For example, surah al-Fatihah, al-Masad, al-Kafirun, and so on, which are suitable for beginners. Overall, the content included in this audiobook model includes the meaning, history, types and recitation practice. For the recitation of the verses of the Qur'an, it is necessary to include a short and easy-to-sing surah or verse that can be followed by beginners.

The *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook model produced is the latest innovation that is different from previous models such as applications and courseware. The prior literature has discovered that no audiobook model was designed and implemented specifically in learning *Tarannum*, and most existing audiobooks only focused on *tajwid* and *qiraat* knowledge. Thus, this study's audiobook model could create an effective and efficient medium for beginners who want to learn the basics of *Tarannum*. It will contribute to the design of the future audiobook that will be specially developed for those who are beginners and would like to learn deeper in this exciting field of *Tarannum*. The real audiobook can provide convenient yet accurate guidance on the knowledge of *Tarannum* as it should be user-friendly regardless of the user's background and age. Apart from that, this audiobook model is very much needed to facilitate *Tarannum* learning in schools, especially for *Kelas Kemahiran Al-Quran* (KKQ). Using audiobooks as teaching aids can further facilitate teachers and students to continue the learning session smoothly and easily. This is because the audiobook can be used as an additional reference to teachers who might be less skilled in the field of *Tarannum*.

For the continuation of this project, this audiobook model is expected to be converted into a prototype to facilitate users in learning *Tarannum*. From prototype development, the actual *Tarannum* audiobook with complete functionality will be created. Perhaps, this audiobook prototype could be distributed worldwide to assist Muslims in *Tarannum* learning. This study not only aims to improve the learning method but also to attract people to deepen the knowledge of *Tarannum* in line with technological advances. In addition, many users will benefit from it, especially beginners with no basic in *Tarannum* to start learning this knowledge, may it be students, parents, teachers or the general public. In the future, the real *Tarannum* audiobook should include a better syllabus, for example, in terms of verses of Surahs and its contents. Besides, it can also include the voices of various reciters as another attraction for people to learn *Tarannum*. Future researchers are also expected to develop a *Tarannum* audiobook according to skill levels such as from beginner to medium and advanced level.

In conclusion, *Tarannum* is one of the most important Holy Qur'an knowledge that must be learned by Muslims. There are plentiful benefits of it, mainly to beautify one's recitation of the Qur'an and it is also the *Sunnah* of the Prophet Muhammad S.A.W. Therefore, this study is intended to help Muslims to learn *Tarannum* knowledge in a convenient, engaging and effective way. As a result, a *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook model has been developed, containing the fundamental knowledge of *Tarannum* for Muslims. It is designed to enhance the understanding of beginners on the basics of *Tarannum* knowledge. However, learning *Tarannum* using this audiobook also requires guidance from the real Qur'anic teachers, especially to clarify certain confusions that might arise among users. This audiobook model is an initial step in realizing the development of the real *Tarannum* Interactive Audiobook. It is an innovative product produced as a new method in *Tarannum* learning. It is hoped that using this method, the users especially beginners will be more concentrated and enthusiastic towards *Tarannum*.

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